

8T –The Photon Propagation

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series author will cover a set of theoretical options which will cover new options concerning the nature of propagation using the insight of Bosons to be discrete amount of net curvature, prime isomorphic. These options are allowing an expansion of the ideas regarding the "repulsion" of two Electrons, which is available using altitude operators. That is stating that the emitting Electron allocated an higher altitude while the absorbing Electron will get lower as it aspire the bottom of the curvature ripple which it absorbed.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

The Electron propagation is presented in two different ways in the 8T thesis. The first via a different form of the Feynman diagrams, using arrows and the framework of variational curvature vanishing in summation of even numbers:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e^-)] + \gamma$$

$$e^- \searrow \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow e^- \nearrow$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow (+3)$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (+5) \rightarrow (+3)$$

$$(+3) + N_V = (+3) + 5 = 8$$

$$8 = \text{Even}$$

$$\text{Even} = 0$$

The second is via the photon absorption in a visual means:

The question and the subject matter is why does the electron repeal its other. Why does the Electrons does not get in to the curve which is the photon but rather "escape" to different directions. There exist several whys to do just that. The first is mentioned in the 8T thesis, if the two Electrons would get into the curve, they will aspire the lowest point and meet each other. Such a scenario will lead to a vanishing of the two Electrons, making the primordial impossible to begin with, if we pre-condition the Electrons to propagate photons. That is the Pauli exclusion principle. For that reason, we presented the form of balanced Graviton with indexing the states of the electrons, to ensure they will not meet each other.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{3}) + (\vec{3})] + \gamma + \gamma \rightarrow [(2N_{gravity}) + (\vec{e}^-) + (\vec{e}^-)] + \gamma + \gamma \quad (2.2.C)$$

There is a second way to explain this phenomena, the Electron which absorbed a photon has absorbed a net curvature of prime amount, it will pull the particle toward the curve putting it in a lower height, while the emitting electron just gave up a certain amount on net curvature which will elevate him to the higher direction. Those two heights will not cross, and thus the two electrons will not meet. This explanation can be put mathematical rigor.

Define the absorbing Electron using the Quantum manifold setting, i.e. using subscripts for classifying the absorbing/emitting elements and superscripts for the number of elements within the Electron.

$$\mathcal{H}_A: (e_K^{-0} \leftarrow \gamma) \rightarrow e_K^{-1}$$

$$\mathcal{H}_E: (e_K^{-1} \rightarrow \gamma) \rightarrow e_K^{-0}$$

Allocate the elevation parameter due to absorption by a term:

$$e_1^{-0} - e_1^{-1} = \Delta \downarrow$$

Allocate the opposite parameter due to emission:

$$e_2^{-1} - e_2^{-0} = \Delta \uparrow$$

Using the following idea, it is possible to imagine a new form of interaction between the Electrons. In such that they can pass on the same spatial coordinates but in different heights. The photon is pulling the absorbed particle to a lower elevation altitude, while its release leading to a higher elevation to the emitting Electron. The Feynman diagram now can be modified:

$$e^- \uparrow \rightarrow (\gamma) \leftarrow e^- \downarrow$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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